

EFFECT OF DIFFERENT FERTILIZER RATES AND APPLICATION TIMINGS ON FIELD GERMINATION AND YIELD OF WINTER WHEAT SEEDS

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Increasing the productivity of agricultural crops in Uzbekistan requires the rational use of water and other resources on every hectare of cultivated land. In addition, the development and cultivation of early-maturing and high-yielding crop varieties, the application of advanced agrotechnologies, measures to combat soil salinity, irrigation and wind erosion, and activities aimed at improving soil fertility are of great importance [1–6].

In this regard, determining the effectiveness of phosphorus and potassium fertilizers, including their application rates, timing, and methods under the meadow-gray soil conditions of the Kashkadarya region, is considered one of the urgent issues in winter wheat cultivation.

Seeds of the winter soft wheat variety G'ozg'on, with a laboratory germination rate of 98%, were sown in mid-October (15 October) at a density of 500 seeds per square meter. During the autumn growing period, phosphorus and potassium fertilizers were applied either simultaneously with sowing in mid-October (15 October), at the beginning of November (1 November), or in mid-November (15 November) (Table).

According to the data presented in the table, it was established that the earlier the seeds of the winter soft wheat variety G'ozg'on were sown in autumn, the more rapid their field germination became, depending on the rates and application timings of phosphorus and potassium fertilizers. Consequently, yield indicators also increased accordingly.

When wheat seeds were sown in mid-October together with the recommended rates of phosphorus and potassium fertilizers, field germination reached up to 82.4% after eight days. This indicator was approximately 1% higher than that observed in the control treatment where phosphorus and potassium fertilizers were not applied. Although this increase was not substantial, it demonstrates that the fertilizers applied at sowing, after irrigation, dissolved in water and entered the soil solution, thereby improving the agro-physical condition of the soil and indirectly promoting seed germination.

However, when phosphorus and potassium fertilizers were applied on 1 November and 15 November in the experimental treatments where wheat had been sown in mid-October, almost no differences were observed in the field

germination of the G'ozg'on wheat seeds. Under these conditions, no noticeable indirect effect of the applied phosphorus and potassium fertilizers on seed germination was detected.

This can be explained by the fact that in experimental treatments 5–12, field germination was determined on 23 October, five days after sowing on 15 October. Therefore, the differences in field germination observed in Table 3.1.1 can be regarded as being within the range of permissible experimental error commonly accepted in field research.

For this reason, it is reasonable to limit the discussion of the table data mainly to experimental treatments 1–4.

Nevertheless, as noted above, the field germination of seeds of the winter soft wheat variety G'ozg'on was positively influenced by the phosphorus and potassium fertilizers applied at sowing. As these fertilizers dissolved in the soil solution, they contributed to the creation of favorable agro-physical conditions for seed germination. This effect can be expressed by the increase in field germination of up to 2% compared with the control treatment where phosphorus and potassium fertilizers were not applied.

Table 1

Effect of Field Germination on the Yield of Wheat (G'ozg'on variety) Seeds Fertilized with Different Rates and at Different Application Times (Average for 2015–2017)

№	Indicators Experimental variants	Autumn growing period (according to the experiment)		Spring growing period (according to recommendation)	Laboratory germination of seeds	Rate/speed of field germination of seeds			Field germination of seeds, %	Yield, c/ha (centners per hectare)
		R ₂ O ₅	K ₂ O	N		After 6 days	After 7 days	After 8 days		
Application of phosphorus and potassium fertilizers on 15 October (at sowing)										
1	N ₀ P ₀ K ₀ (st)	0	0	0	500	405	406	407	81,4	35,4
2	N ₁₅₀ P ₇₀ K ₅₀	70	50	150	500	406	408	409	84,8	59,5
3	N ₁₈₀ P ₉₀ K ₆₀	90	60	180	500	407	410	410	82,0	64,2
4	N ₂₁₀ P ₁₀₅ K ₇₀	105	70	210	500	408	411	412	82,4	71,3
Application of phosphorus and potassium fertilizers on 1 November (15 days after sowing)										
5	N ₀ P ₀ K ₀ (st)	0	0	0	500	400	403	405	81,0	35,2
6	N ₁₅₀ P ₇₀ K ₅₀	70	50	150	500	401	404	406	81,2	57,3
7	N ₁₈₀ P ₉₀ K ₆₀	90	60	180	500	402	405	406	81,2	61,1
8	N ₂₁₀ P ₁₀₅ K ₇₀	105	70	210	500	402	406	407	81,4	66,8

Application of phosphorus and potassium fertilizers on 15 November (30 days after sowing)										
9	N ₀ P ₀ K ₀ (st)	0	0	0	500	392	395	397	79,4	35,0
10	N ₁₅₀ P ₇₀ K ₅₀	70	50	150	500	393	396	398	79,6	50,5
11	N ₁₈₀ P ₉₀ K ₆₀	90	60	180	500	395	397	399	79,8	54,0
12	N ₂₁₀ P ₁₀₅ K ₇₀	105	70	210	500	396	398	400	80,0	58,9

In conclusion, under the unfavorable soil and climatic conditions of Kashkadarya region for agriculture, when seeds of the winter soft wheat variety G'ozg'on are sown in mid-October (15 October) and phosphorus and potassium fertilizers are applied simultaneously with sowing, the dissolution of these fertilizers in the soil solution improves the agro-physical properties of the soil. As a result, field germination increases by up to 2% compared with the control treatment where mineral fertilizers were not applied.

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